
Feel Guides and Feel Heals in Neuropsy Power Meditation - Meditation is Not Same Everywhere and for Everyone

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ABSTRACT

Meditation is an umbrella term and there are varieties of techniques. Many similarities are found and most of the meditations either 'intentional thought handling' or 'intentional thought suppression' is the major tool of the procedure. In Neuropsy Power meditation, none of these two nor sensory stimuli are employed. There are also other differences between Neuropsy Power meditation on one hand and all other meditations on the other. It is necessary, to highlight the differences and elaborate continuously with newly available knowledge from research and practice. In this paper, the differences between neuropsy Power meditation are highlighted. *Clearly, Neuropsy Meditation is aimed at uncovering originality / uniqueness of an individual and natural heal original to his subjective system, in a natural way polar opposite to banking on voluntary efforts.*

Keywords: Neuropsy Power meditation, Meditation stimulus, Thought Handling, Thought Suppression, Feel

1. This Paper

This paper is aimed at drawing distinctions of Neuropsy Power meditation when compared to other meditations. As this task is essential to disseminate the scientific knowledge base of Neuropsy Power meditation and differentiate it from others, so that it is not confused in understanding. Also, the differences are to be clear in any scientific and research endeavours so that, depth of a technique with distinct characteristics are uncovered.

This paper is confined to the function of 'focusing toward' or 'meditation stimulus' and that secondary to the meditation stimulus. This paper also highlights the differences between Neuropsy Power meditation and other meditations.

1.1. Meditation Stimulus

A meditation stimulus is a 'distinct stimulus of concrete or abstract and internal or external kind upon which voluntary attention is focused' as required in a meditation practice. This definition is in line with universal operation definition of meditation (Ramesh Kumar G S 2022a).

It is understood that meditation has both positive and negative outcomes and normally it is employed for the positive results presumed

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Meditation as such found to be giving positive benefits such as decreasing stress reactivity on a psychological, physiological and neurobiological level (Michaela C. Pascoe et.al 2021), blood pressure and stress in patients with arterial hypertension (Ponte Márquez, P.H., Feliu-Soler, A., Solé-Villa, M.J. etal. 2019) and many more. However, the varieties of meditations are so divergent that there is no “meditation” as such, but there are rather different groups of techniques that might exert diverse effects (Matko,Karin and Sedlmeier, Peter, 2019).

1.2. Initiation

In other meditations, Focused attention (FA) meditation is often practiced when one begins meditation (Ruben E. Laukkonen, and Heleen A. Slagter.,2021). But in Neuropsy Power meditation, the Meditation Psychologist / Guru prepares the case history of the client in detailed clinical model to facilitate understanding for Meditation Psychologist and Client on what is expected by client and where does he / she currently stand in that task or mission.

Neuropsy Power meditation is the only technique which has been developed for individualized, measurable goal-oriented, intervention for achievements in business, politics and crucial health aspects. Therefore, while other meditations begin with introduction and closing of eyes, Neuropsy Power meditation begin with case-history taking, defining Goals for the individual and then followed by “Sankalp” (Resolution). In other words, Neuropsy Power meditation happens on a broad field of wholistic perception, end to end.

Figure 1Showing Initiation in the Overall Process of Neuropsy Power Meditation

1.3. Focus

Attentional control system is an important aspect of comprehensive memory system (Alan D Baddeley., 2021). Attention Focus is usually linked with time spent and whether one’s performance depends on internal or external distractors (Diaz-Orueta, Unai., Blanco-Campal, Alberto., Lamar, Melissa., Libon, David J. and Burke, Teresa, 2020). Of Alerting, Orienting and Executive aspects of Attentional Network, Difficulty inhibiting fear, Dwell on negative ideation, Recurring thoughts, images or behaviors, Negative ideation, lack of control, Hallucinations, Compelled behavior are associated with Executive aspect of Attentional Network (Posner MI., Rothbart MK., and Ghassemzadeh H.2019). Current author inclines to highlight that attention focus in meditation is not to be shut with closing of eyes and concentrating as found in many commercial handouts. Attention Focus and whole gravity of attention should be well understood by the Meditation Guru, as far as Neuropsy Power meditation is concerned, if not in other meditations.

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The chief characteristic of all meditation techniques remains ‘focusing of attention’, and as such it is essential to differentiate a technique on what it focuses, as part of meditation. Even in the so-called “Open Monitoring”, the function of ‘focusing’ is not nullified. Rather, it is toward ‘conscious experiences’ rather than specific sensations as in so-called ‘Focused Attention’ (Brown, K. W., Berry, D., Eichel, K., Beloborodova, P., Rahrig, H. & Britton, W. B. 2022).

Usually focused in other meditations are somatic stimuli such as body sensations, or breathing (Irrmischer, M et.al 2018) or the awareness of breathing touching the body, specific object or in a specific state of mind, such as love or equanimity (Blase KL and van Waning A., 2019). Absolutely different stimulus is being used in the Neuropsy Power meditation, and that stimulus is ‘not imagined, not giving feeling, not visualized nor thought’. Other meditations are also linked to emotional processing (Desbordes G et.al 2012) as focus or Meditation stimulus, while the Neuropsy Power Meditation distances itself from any such concrete stimuli and processes.

Obviously, the Meditation stimulus – on which the client has to focus attention is neither in thought form nor in feeling / emotion, but rather it is a distinct ‘feel’. This is the characteristic, differentiates Neuropsy Power meditation entirely away from all other meditations on the area of ‘focus’ or ‘meditation stimulus’.

Hence, an individual can focus on it only for a few seconds, and altering to emotion/ feeling or any thought is not under the purview of Neuropsy Power Meditation. Therefore, attempting to hold attention only make the individual to slip into other form of meditation unrelated to Neuropsy Power meditation, in any way. This is a point of paradigm difference between Neuropsy Power meditation and other meditations on the whole.

Figure 2. Gap Between Where Am I and What I Want? Should Be Handled By Qualified Psychologist

1.4. Divine Vs Volition:

Divine Vs Volition is differentiating humans, makes a human realize his capabilities and incapacities, Power and limitations, and makes them feel Supreme or Modest (especially, Unassuming and Unpretentious). Every human strives to attain either Power or Association with Power, thereby, to distance oneself from Humble or Perceived Weak States.

Obtaining Power or associating with Power are two different states with their own depth and intricacies of dynamics. But that ‘thirst’ is quenched by (voluntary) efforts. The more one invests or anchored on this notion, he / she keeps increasing voluntary efforts. At the failure, feeling humble instead of powered by voluntary efforts’ might, and submits to some other source that can fulfill desires, in his or her perception.

‘Quenching of such thirst’ is sensed at the ‘innerly feeling a sense of divine strength’ that assures might. This is the core process in other meditations or prayers or yagnas or tapas. But in Neuropsy Power Meditation the Strength is realized not by banking on voluntary efforts fiercely but banking more and more on Modesty – a polar opposite.

In so doing, the person just remains what he or she just is and enhancing his originality / uniqueness to unfurl and manifest, inching towards natural heal.

It is not of ‘I do till or for.....’ but ‘I just remain till my core feel (that cannot be voluntarily maneuvered) guides me and heals me.....that I realize what it is only after getting it’.How swiftly attention turns toward the original stimulus, away from the distraction is an important trajectory and is assessed using subjective scales in line with Psychometry. This is also why a psychologist qualified to the core alone can be the trainer.

1.5. *Unexpected Solutions*

This condition nullifies the effects of expectancy or habit or fluency and ensures strictly the effect of Neuropsy Power Meditation, in its pure form. It is to be remembered that, such effects are unexpected to the consciousness of the individual – meaning he / she will not know till it comes to his conscious sphere and are not voluntary at all. The heal / solution is unplanned and involuntary, realized only after it happens, *initiated by core feel*.

2. Secondary To Focus

2.1 Thought Suppression

Though meditators are viewed better than normal, experienced meditators show insignificant level of benefits on performing certain visual attention tasks than the controls (Devaney, K.J et.al (2021). But it doesn't mean that no categorical difference exists. With regard to sustained attention, the activities of dorsal attention and default mode networks can be found to be varied when compared to controls. Thus, it is established that meditators do differ from controls in certain respects and not behave like aliens totally. Of course, the areas of differences are still to be dug and more to be revealed convincingly.

As of the researchers, the DMN suppression is to be considered and linked to the benefits, or at least differences during meditation process.

Their findings indicate that experience in meditation causes no difference in either reaction time to reorienting spatially to a sudden and new target, or cortical activation in the ventral attention network when distracted by sudden and new target. But in another study, there was shorter reaction time reported for meditators (Kazuki Yoshida et.al 2020).

These positively stimulates to doubt, if 'meditation alone' is effective or 'any thought suppression' would be fair enough to produce desirable results. In such a case, then, it is not meditation technique solely responsible for the desired results, but meditation merely remains a method of thought suppression like any other. Importantly, it is to be ascertained whether the meditative process brings changes in the structure of the brain which in turn bring change in behaviour or the transient changes during meditation, instigate the 'guidelines / norms' of expected behaviour and expectancy effect be activated in many occasions or a combination of these two. Indication of transient changes due to meditation is also reported elsewhere (Srinivasan, N. & Bajjal, S. (2007).

In Neuropsy Power meditation, clients are not encouraged to do pile up voluntary efforts including focusing on thoughts, analysis, comparison, contrasting or suppression or banking on psychosomatic efforts. These are the *Self-Impositions* seen as roots of pathology (Ramesh Kumar G S 2022a).

There is need for studying deeper in line with advocated intricacy psychology (Ramesh Kumar, G S 2022) of sustained changes and transient changes due to meditation and different types of meditation procedures. Hence, using meditation as an umbrella term is quite misleading as far as psychological and neuropsychological researches are concerned. In this background, the suggestion of long-term practice (Martínez, Vivot R et.al 2020) for benefit itself remains a partially convinced notion. Though the researchers identified four types of alterations in the meditators' perception of reality as induced by tranquility and insight, genuineness of experiences and their purity are suspected (Full, G.E., Walach, H and Trautwein(2013). This kind of complicated nature revolving around the processes involved and routes of benefits in meditation often point a need for intricacy psychology approach.

Apart from such intricate junctures, considering the side of benefits, it has to be endorsed that even the transient changes help to some extent. We cannot ignore the benefits that especially help in the alteration of existing perceptions mainly reappraisal. Such alterations are distinguished (another point of intricacy) from thought suppressions and attributed to mindfulness training, though transient (Garland EL et.al 2015). Thus, whether transient or not, whether for more experienced or fairly experienced, the starting point of meditation benefits seems to be temporary suspension of thoughts and enhancement of appraisal / reappraisal, through such suspension of thoughts, on the surface level.

It is also to remember everyone's experience that when some time is allowed to divert the thoughts and resume later, the older emotions are found to be moderated and often the perspectives too. Thus, diversion and suppression are two forms intertwined sometimes to give the same perceptual alterations. Question of whether meditation remains solely responsible or merely like any other method of thought suppression, persists.

Whereas in Neuropsy Power meditation, since dealing with thought in any manner is discouraged, appraisal or reappraisal is also discouraged. Rather, it is that the 'Feel Guides, Feel Heals'. Feel is different from feeling or even 'core affect'(Ramesh Kumar G S 2022b)

2.2. *Duration*

In Neuropsy Power meditation, it is not half-an-hour or 45 minutes or 1 hour per occasion of meditation, as in other meditations. Hence, it is doubtful to what extent sustained training for long time, fit the case of Neuropsy Power meditation, while it is usually warranted in other forms of meditation (Rodríguez-Larios J., Bracho Montes de Oca EA, and Alaerts K 2021). Recently, even 5 minutes of mindfulness found to be helpful in some way, for example in abolishing self-bias by Golubickis, et.al (2022).

The coaching session is planned for 30 minutes or 60 minutes. But the time, a client takes at home or work place for one instance of meditation is just a

few minutes. This is because, it was developed keeping in mind the individuals running short of time like professionals, politicians, and business executives. In fact, the clients are encouraged to take up meditation instances during their work schedule every 5 minutes or 10 minutes, for a duration of one or two minutes. The meditation stimulus in Neuropsy Power Meditation is such a delicate one that they could attend to it only a few seconds and they 'can never claim to hold it on'. Sooner their meditation would slip into other forms of meditation completely unrelated to Neuropsy Power meditation.

2.3. Philosophical Roots

Philosophical roots of meditation in general and therefore, that of Neuropsy Power meditation are deep and cannot be dealt with here completely, but can only be hinted. Current author's wish and argument here is that much of the energy and efforts should not be invested on techniques for transient changes and sustenance solely depending on sustained use of such techniques. Also, meditations are originally based on the Hindu philosophies such as Advaita. These Hindu philosophies, though have some apparent similarities, are different from western ones such as Husserl's (Surya Kanta Maharana, 2009).

Peeling out from umbrella term of meditation, the specific ones that have roots in eastern philosophies cannot be viewed merely as techniques, but broader systems, and commercially there are so many "Meditation Gurus", claiming to be certified and trained for some hours or a few days. It is unbelievable how the meditation, the juncture of meeting between deeper philosophy on one hand and psychology including neuropsychology on the other hand, is mastered by some non-psychologists in few days. Whereas, the current system of Neuropsy Power meditation relies on continua or stages of everything and anything associated or coupled, in turn, form a continuum in between (Ramesh Kumar G S 1999). It is the continua between "I" and "object" rather than whether "I" and "Object" are same or separated (Neither Dvaita., ie Dualistic nor Advaita., ie Monistic).

This needs some explanation with some examples for easy understanding by the researchers and even common man. The basic philosophy of Neuropsy Power meditation holds that both monistic (Advait) and Dualistic (Dvait) arguments thoroughly rests on discrete view of the objects. For example, one (monistic) Vs two (Dvait) mean countable nature and therefore discrete. Neuropsy Power Meditation rests on 'unified' or 'coalesced' nature of the entities. When two individuals respond in two different ways to tiger in their close vicinity, the behaviour is discrete but the intricacies of dynamics of every single behaviour is constituting coalesced intricacies of dynamics of contributions from personality, motivation, intelligence etc.

Only when the surface behaviour is considered, monistic or dualistic distinction of discreteness emerges. But, when the 'constituent' is considered, there is no discreteness rather the coalesced nature without horizon rules the scenario. This is the underpinning for Seamless Time Focus (Ramesh Kumar G S, 2022). When coalescence results seamlessly then even the 'one' cannot be contrasted from. When such seamless coalescence exists, there is neither 'I' nor 'You', nor 'it', nor 'they'. This is beyond the time also, i.e., neither 'present' nor 'past/future'. Without understanding the shallowness or gravity of these concepts, one cannot become the 'Meditation Guru' or 'Meditation Psychologist' for administering Neuropsy Power Meditation.

Similarly, when a learner or client attempts for Neuropsy Power meditation, there will be a gap between what he does (achieved) and what actually ought to occur (to be achieved). In Neuropsy Power Meditation, it is brought to the fore by the question of 'What you did, and what happened?' by the Meditation Psychologist towards the client, on every instance of meditation coaching. Though, the client could give some surface level answer, the duty of the Meditation Psychologist is to guess the 'amount of gap', and 'shallowness or gravity of the gap'. This once again is not to be camouflaged by assumptions or layman theories, but to be analyzed from the view of a Psychologist qualified to the core. Instead of all these professional works, if the meditation Psychologist shares the same stage positioned by client, then, there is no need for a 'coach' or 'Guru' at all.

In the Neuropsy Power meditation, the change or solution is awaited and the individual doesn't know till it comes. He doesn't meditate on the pre-conceived solution or wish. This suddenness is as similar as any sudden stimulus. This stage is very vital and has intricacies of dynamics within inherently. For example, in case of sudden stimuli in lab, meditators took more Reaction Time than non – meditators (Devaney, K.J et.al.2021). In Neuropsy Power Meditation, it is often responded swiftly, as observation and verification are discouraged when mind highlights an answer – it is only ready acceptance and therefore the Reaction Time is ignored aspect actually. Neuropsy Power meditation also discourages the voluntary appraisal or reappraisal. It also discourages the Observation, Verification, Analysis etc. during meditative process (Ramesh Kumar G S 2023).

Figure 3. The Gap Between What Client Tries and What Actually Happens in Each Instance is Very Crucial in Neuropsy Power Meditation

2.4. Personality and Processing

Effects of Focused Attention meditation depend on prior experience with the task such that Focused Attention meditation modulates 'gain control principles in information processing' (Ullrich, S., Colzato, L.S., Wolff, N. et al 2021). In Neuropsy Power meditation, every moment is new and the individual does not use anything repeatedly, and voluntary processes such as analyses or control are suspended.

In fact, the Meditation Psychologist asks after every trial instance which last from a few seconds to a few minutes, 'What did you do and what happened?'. This is the only question, and answer by the client is analyzed psychologically. It should be remembered that due to variation in cortical activity in introverts and extroverts, the perceived pleasantness of induced arousal level will also differ (Lehmann, JAM, Hamm, V, Seufert, T2019), adding to complex psychological analyses. Such personality of the individual, is a global organization and therefore measuring the results while administering meditation as a group could very well be biased. Thus, anyone, other than a psychologist qualified to the core, cannot handle this technique judiciously and there is no room for personal assumptions nor layman psychology, strictly. Thus, Neuropsy Power meditation is a highly professional and scientific technique to be implemented to clients only by Psychologists qualified to the core.

2.5. Distractions

The distractions and wandering of mind, that a client report and along with the involuntary recoveries of some past memories are the representations of those events. Hence, such 'distractions' and 'wandering of mind', are highly important for a Meditation Psychologist / Meditation Guru, as far as Neuropsy Power meditation coaching is concerned. They are 'subjective representations' and personalized by the client. Such representations underlying an experience are inhibited by prefrontal control causes forgetting (Michael C. Anderson., Justin C. Hulbert. 2021). They are viewed as 'personalized representations' and dealt with the depth and intricacies of their dynamics, realizing that the 'pattern' of each individual regarding his or her "personalized representations" speak much about each client to understand uniqueness of client and deciding how to coach (individualized) on Neuropsy Power Meditation. Such 'personalized representations' or distractions should be differentiated. For example, Christoff, K., Irving, Z., Fox, K. et al (2016), differentiates between mind wandering and ruminations based on their intricacies of dynamics.

Figure 4. "Distractions" Are "Personalized Representations" and are Very Crucial

His, distractions in others' terms, and global 'personal representations' with their depth and intricacies of dynamics in Neuropsychology Power meditation, that existed as of date prevented him / her from attaining a self-growth / solution. Neglecting them, over sight, undermining them cannot be a fool proof approach.

2.6. Benefits

Administration of (i) breathing meditation/ body scan, (ii) loving-kindness, and (iii) observing-thought, meditations and analyses of the results have been discussed by Kok, B.E and Singer, T (2017). But a close scrutiny gives two impressions. One, the results are generalizable to group and not individualized(or at least ignored) and second, that 'what we train over a period of time, we get'.

In Neuropsychology Power Meditation, first of all, the group session is out of bounds, since it is an intervention meditation. Second, the individuals get results to their personal situations and cannot be generalized. Thirdly, and importantly, the results are not trained.

3. Discussion

In this paper, various aspects on which Neuropsychology Power Meditation differs from other meditation are highlighted. Neuropsychology Power meditation differs from other meditations in many aspects starting from Initiation itself. A noteworthy statement is beautifully dealt with by Sörqvist P (2015) stressing that 'definition' of an effect is about the difference between two (or more) conditions whilst an explanation is a theory about why this difference arises. This is employed in every instance of meditation coaching, by the Meditation Psychologist while administering Neuropsychology Power meditation. Unlike other meditations, with mere few days / weeks of training one cannot become a Meditation Guru. In Neuropsychology Power Meditation, only psychologists already qualified to the core can become Meditation Guru / Meditation Psychologist.

In other meditations, either intentional thought handling or intentional thought suppression is the major tool of the procedure. Intentional focus on any simple internal task may inhibit the early stages of memory consolidation (Collins MB, Wamsley EJ 2020) in the absence of any obvious increase in hippocampal encoding of new experience. In Neuropsychology Power Meditation it is 'feel', as differentiated from 'feeling' and emotion, is the meditation stimulus. No form of sensory or other concrete stimuli or thoughts are involved for the purpose of meditation stimulus. But what usually, happens as a benefit of Neuropsychology Power meditation is that activation of even long forgotten memories coming to conscious awareness randomly and vividly without any efforts. This particular revisit of younger days' moments now and then to be studied in future with respect to brain activation. This increased past memories involuntarily is not reported in other meditations.

Clients do enjoy such memories and even if they get negative memories, they automatically tend to either put aside or enjoy the nostalgia, without getting affected emotionally. This is also an area to be studied in deep in future. Usually viewed by other meditations as 'distractions' or 'mind wandering' and dealt with at surface levels are given high importance in Neuropsy Power Meditations. Clearly, Neuropsy Meditation is aimed at uncovering originality / uniqueness of an individual and natural heal original to his subjective system, in a natural way polar opposite to banking on voluntary efforts.

Further elaboration on each aspect needs to be scrutinized in future.

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